

SUPERSATURATION LIMITS OF SOLUTIONS. PART IV. THE EFFECT OF HEATING ON THE LIMITS OF SUPERSATURATION

BY RAM GOPAL

The effect of heating on the limits of supersaturation of aqueous solutions of a number of substances has been investigated. Heating, in general, stabilises solutions against spontaneous crystallisation; but solutions of KCl, KBr, KI and KNO_3 etc. exhibit a very small or negligible heating effect. An explanation to the above anomaly is suggested by considering the concentration (c) of the solute and viscosity (η or $1/\eta = \phi$) of the medium. Roughly speaking, if the $c\phi$ values for any solution are greater than 30, the heating effect is negligible.

Certain marked exceptions to the $c\phi$ rule are noticed, specially in organic solutes and ammonium salts. These are accounted for by the low mutual affinity among the molecules of the solutes.

In previous communications the author (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 20, 187; 1944, 21, 104) has observed that, in general, $T_s - T$ (where T_s denotes the saturation temperature and T , the temperature of spontaneous crystallisation of a solution) increases with number and degree of heating. Several workers (Schaum, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1898, 25, 722; Schaum and Schoenbeck, *Ann. Physik*, 1902, 8, 655; Füchtbauer, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1904, 48, 549; Young and Burke, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1907, 29, 329; Issac, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1908, 93, 364; Marcelin, *Compt. rend.*, 1910, 148, 631; Othmer, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1915, 91, 209; Kornfeld, *Monatsh.*, 1916, 37, 609; Hinshelwood and Hartley, *Phil. Mag.*, 1922, 43, 78; Schaum and Riffert, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1922, 190, 241; Richards, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 54, 479; Richards, Kirkpatrick and Hutz, *ibid.*, 1936, 58, 2243) have studied this problem but nearly all of them have confined themselves to the study of crystallisation of organic melts under prolonged heating. Their results appear to show that prolonged heating, in general, increases the limit of undercooling. However, a detailed study of solutions on these lines is almost lacking. It appears therefore desirable to study solutions from this viewpoint in order to collect data which will elucidate this anomalous behaviour (i.e. negligible effect of preheating on the limits of supersaturation of the solutions of KNO_3 , KBr, KI etc.).

EXPERIMENTAL

Sealed tubes containing solutions of different substances at some known saturation temperature (T_s) were prepared in the same way as described in a previous communication (*loc. cit.*, 1943) and were heated in a beaker of water at 80° to 90° for various periods of time. They were shaken with hand vigorously from time to time as no suitable equipment could be conveniently fitted up for shaking them continuously while heating. The temperature of spontaneous crystallisation (T) was determined in the usual manner. Results for typical substances of the two groups are given in Table I.

TABLE I

(Hours of heating are given in brackets; * denotes that crystallisation did not occur down to this temperature.)

G R O U P I.			
1. Potassium iodide.		2. Potassium bromide.	
T_3 .	T .	T_3 .	T .
80	64.0 (2), 64.4(6), 63.6 (11), 63.8 (14).	80	62.0 (6), 62.2 (10), 62.5 (16).
66	49.0 (2), 48.8 (11), 49.0 (14).	75	59.4 (6), 59.6 (10), 59.4 (16).
60	44.6 (2), 44.0 (6), 43.8 (11), 44.4 (11).	58	41.6 (2), 41.8 (11), 40.0 (16).
55 (7)	44.6 (2), 45.0 (5), 44.0 (11), 44.0 (14).	50	34.0 (6), 33.8 (16), 33.8 (20).
50	34.2 (2), 33.8 (5), 33.6 (11), 33.2 (14).	45	28.4 (6), 28.0 (10), 23.0 (16).
3. Potassium nitrate.		4. Sodium nitrate.	
75	60.2 (3), 61.0 (6), 60.0 (12).	70	67.2 (3), 67.0 (8), 67.4 (15).
70	55.0 (3), 55.6 (6), 56.0 (12).	66	61.2 (6), 62.0 (10), 61.0 (12).
60	47.0 (3), 46.8 (6), 46.0 (12).	60	45.2 (6), 44.0 (10), 44.0 (12).
50	36.2 (3), 36.0 (6), 35.4 (12).	50	3.8 (6), 37.2 (10), 36.0 (12), 35.8 (16).
45	32.0 (3), 31.4 (6), 31.0 (12).	45	30.6 (6), 30.0 (10), 30.2 (12).
G R O U P II.			
1. Barium nitrate.		2. Barium chloride.	
75	45.2 (1), 40.6 (2), 32.8 (3), *30.0 (6), *25.0 (6).	80	50.2 (2), 48.6 (4), 35.6 (6).
70	43.8 (1), 37.2 (2), *25.0 (3), *25.2 (5).	75	42.6 (2), 36.6 (4), *30.4 (6).
66	4.00 (1), 36.0 (2), *31.0 (3), 37.0 (4), *27.2 (6).	70	34.2 (2), *25. (4), *20.0 (6).
60	33.8 (1), 30.7 (2), *15.0 (4).	65	30.0 (2), 26.4 (4), *22.6 (6).
55	30.0 (1), 27.4 (2), 29.0 (4), *26.0 (5).	60	26.2 (2), *25.2 (4), *20.0 (6).
3. Potassium dichromate.		4. Potassium oxalate.	
75	42.2 (2), 38.0 (6), 61.2 (12), 56.0 (16).	80	40.2 (2), 30.2 (6), *26.0 (14).
66	15.0 (2), 40.2 (4), 30.0 (6), 31.2 (12), 25.8 (16).	75	37.4 (2), 32.2 (6), *26.0 (14).
55	30.8 (2), 40.2 (4), 30.0 (6), 20.0 (15).	70	30.2 (2), *26.0 (6), *24.0 (14).
50	26.6 (2), 23.0 (4), 20.4 (9), *18.0 (15).	66	28.4 (2), 20.8 (6), *18.0 (14).
40	32.0 (2), *19.6 (3), *16.0 (6).	60	*25.0 (2), *25 (6).
5. Thiourea.		6. Benzoic acid.	
70	44.0 (4), 37.6 (12), 34.2 (6).	75	53.2 (2), 35.0 (6), 53.2 (14).
66	45.8 (4), 33.0 (10), *30.0 (16).	70	45.0 (2), 40.0 (6), 37.8 (14).
60	32.2 (8), 39.2 (12), 26.8 (16).	66	42.0 (2), 40.2 (6), 36.0 (14).
55	28.4 (6), 23.2 (12), 20.0 (16).	60	34.0 (2), 30.6 (6), *25.0 (14).
50	35.2 (8), *29.0 (4), *25.4 (6).	55	31.2 (2), *26.0 (6), *24.2 (6) 32.8 (14).

From the examples cited in Table I and numerous other cases, which have been omitted here for the sake of brevity, it appears that the effect of heating in increasing the limits of supersaturation $T_s - T$ is a very general phenomenon as has been observed in the case of organic melts by other workers (*loc. cit.*) and that only a few isolated cases show a small or negligible heating effect. The complete results of the investigation are summarised in Table II.

TABLE II

Substances showing a very small or negligible heating effect.

KCl*, KBr, KI, NaNO₃,
KNO₃, KClO₄.

Substances with considerable heating effect.

Ba(NO₃)₂, BaCl₂, KIO₃, K₂Cr₂O₇, KClO₃, KBrO₃,
K₄Fe(CN)₆, K₃Fe(CN)₆, NH₄Cl, (NH₄)₂SO₄, K₂C₂O₄,
(NH₄)₂C₂O₄, H₂U₂O₄, CO(NH₂)₂, CS(NH₂)₂,
C₆H₅.COOH, NH₄NO₂** , KCN etc. etc.

* Heating effect is appreciable in some tubes.

** " " appears negligible specially at higher T_s .

DISCUSSION

According to Hinshelwood and Hartley (*loc. cit.*) the heating effect is due to decrease in the catalytic activity of the colloidal dust particles* which are derived from air. These particles are considered to be surrounded by an orientated adsorbed layer. This system acts as a fragment of a pure crystal in initiating spontaneous crystallisation. If large enough, the system is active immediately, if not, a series of fortunate chances are required in order that a crystal of necessary size may be formed. The degree of dispersion of the active colloidal particles is supposed to change irreversibly with preheating, time and other experimental conditions. Recent developments of this theory have been proposed by Richards and his co-workers (*loc. cit.*) to suit their experimental observations. For our purpose, however, only the hypothesis of Hinshelwood and Hartley, coupled with the molecular kinetic conceptions of de Coppet and G. Tammann about the formation of an active crystalline nucleus, appears to be more suitable and general and hence an attempt has been made to explain the different behaviours of the two classes of solutes mentioned above on these grounds.

* A very convincing and direct experimental evidence in favour of the dust particle theory is found in the filtration effects on the spontaneous crystallisation of supercooled systems. This aspect of the problem has been investigated by Jaffé (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1903, 48, 686), Führtbauer (*ibid.*, 1904, 48, 549), Meyer and Pfaff (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1934, 217, 267; 1935, 222, 382; 1935, 224, 304) and by Tammann and Buchner (*ibid.*, 1935, 222, 370). Filtration which removes dust particles, has been shown to stabilise supercooled systems against the chances of spontaneous crystallisation.

According to the well known kinetic molecular hypothesis, the formation of a crystalline nucleus is a probability phenomenon and a nucleus comes into stable existence when the lattice forming units collide in a sufficient number so as to produce a particle big enough to be stable at any particular temperature. This process will be aided by the dust particles which might act as adsorbents or simple heat carriers in the inelastic molecular collision or in some other mysterious fashion not yet clearly understood. The probability of formation of a crystalline nucleus cannot be exactly defined, nevertheless, it is possible to state qualitatively that it will be greater, (i) greater the concentration of the solute, (ii) greater the concentration of the dust particles or inductor, (iii) greater the volume of the system employed, (iv) greater the duration of the experiment i.e. smaller the rate of cooling, and (v) smaller the viscosity of the medium etc.

In order to obtain the relative values of the limits of supersaturation, conditions (iii) and (iv), i.e. the volume and the rate of cooling, have been kept similar in all the experiments and therefore their effect has been eliminated. Hence factors (i), (ii) and (v) will be effective in differentiating various systems.

The concentration of the dust particles (v) may be taken to be the same in all the cases in the beginning of the experiments and this will be gradually lowered in the process of heating and shaking. On the other hand, the concentration of the solute will remain constant depending only on its solubility. Due to lowering in the concentration of the inductor, the number of successful molecular collisions will go on diminishing in a definite time as the process of heating, shaking, crystallisation and redissolution is continued. If this probability is lowered to such an extent that no successful molecular collision occurs during the time of cooling, the temperature of spontaneous crystallisation will go on lowering with the amount of heating etc.

If the concentration of the solute is very high, however, the number of successful collision may still be very large even though some of the dust particles have been removed from the active field. It means that the time required for a successful collision may still be very small as compared to the rate of cooling. In other words, crystallisation should start at the previous temperature of spontaneous crystallisation after which the heating has been performed. Hence we see that although number or effectiveness of dust particles is being gradually reduced by heating and shaking etc., spontaneous crystallisation is yet possible at the original degree of supercooling if the concentration of the solute is very high. This appears to be the main cause of the anomaly referred to in Table II. Filtration appears to be more effective agency in this process, as after five to six operations a lowering in T has been noticed in solutions of KNO_3 by Jaffé (*loc. cit.*) while they show negative effect in our case.

The viscosity η of the medium will oppose the molecular collisions or its reverse ϕ (fluidity) will favour them. Hence fluidity like concentration will also control the molecular collisions. Their product may therefore be expected to

lead to an expression which may be closely related with the capacity of forming active centres in a system provided all collisions are successful. This is detailed in Table III in which the concentration c is expressed in g. mol. of solute per 100 g. of solvent[‡], η ($1/\phi$) values are taken from an unpublished work on 'the viscosity of supersaturated solutions' by the author. The viscosity corresponds generally to the most probable temperature of the first spontaneous crystallisation and hence they are mostly intrapolated figures. The same temperature of saturation T_s (50°) has been considered in all the cases.

TABLE III

Solute.	$T_s - T^*$	η † at 1st. T_s	$\frac{Sw_{1,2}^*}{M}$ = c .	ϕ (or c/η)	Solute.	$T_s - T^*$	η † at 1st. T_s	$\frac{Sw_{1,2}^*}{M}$ = c .	ϕ (or c/η).
KCl	19.5	0.00930	0.572	61.5	$K_2C_2O_4$	30.0	0.01800	0.2950	15.5
KBr	16.0	0.00876	0.686	79.4	$Ba(NO_3)_2$	18.0	0.00920	0.0655	8.9
KI	15.5	0.00980	1.000	102.0	$BaCl_2$	25.0	0.01450	0.2070	14.8
$KClO_4$	6.5	0.00600	0.0369	6.12	$NaClO_4$	14.0	0.03700	0.8970	24.2
KNO_3	13.0	0.01030	0.8520	82.7	Oxalic acid	15.0	0.01160	0.2992	34.4
$NaNO_3$	13.0	0.0258	0.8370	32.7	KIO_3	14.0	0.00800	0.0768	9.6
$KClO_3$	8.0	0.00845	0.1580	24.6	$HgCl_2$	23.2	0.00860	0.0420	4.9
$KBrO_3$	9.4	0.00670	0.0461	0.9	Succinic acid	2.00	0.01280	0.2067	16.5
$K_2Cr_2O_7$	12.0	0.00810	0.1180	14.7	Benzoic acid	17.8	0.00770	0.0086	0.84
$K_3Fe(CN)_6$	12.8	0.01340	0.1970	14.7	Salicylic acid	20.0	0.0.790	0.0058	0.76
$K_4Fe(CN)_6$	20.0	0.01380	0.1160	8.9	Urea ($T_s = 40^\circ$)	15.0	0.02770(Taimini)	2.5	110.0
NH_4Cl	20.0	0.00940	0.9530	101.4	Thiourea	11.2	0.00880	0.68	78.7
Am_2SO_4	20.0	0.02600	0.6860	24.4	NH_4NO_3	11.0	0.029.0	4.56	157.0
Am .oxalate	12.4	0.00880	0.1050	12.3	KCNS	13.2	0.04300	3.30	78.7

Table III clearly shows that the value of $c\phi$, in cases where heating effect is very small or negligible, lies well above 30 except in $KClO_4$ for which it is 6.1. Where heating effect is well marked, the values of $c\phi$ lie, in general, below 20. Here again we meet with exceptions in ammonium salts and organic substances which, inspite of high $c\phi$ values, show considerable heating effect. However, inspite of these exceptions the difference in the $c\phi$ values of the two classes, in general, is so marked as to leave no doubt about the predominant effect of

‡ Concentration should be expressed by volume but as all other considerations are only highly approximate, it is perhaps superfluous to be too accurate in this case.

* T denotes the first temperature of spontaneous crystallisation.

† Intrapolated to the required temperature if crystallisation occurs earlier as happens in most of the solutions of low viscosity.

concentration and viscosity on this phenomenon. Reviewing we can state qualitatively that if the concentration of the solute is very high and at the same time viscosity of the system is low, the heating effect will be very small or negligible (i. e. $T_s - T$ should be approximately constant). On the other hand, if the viscosity of the system is high or concentration low or both, heating effect will be marked.

The exceptions remain to be explained. Uptil now we have been considering molecules and ions as simple neutral particles of matter, identical in all cases without any specific or individual characteristic of their own. When we come to concrete cases, this simplified view demands modification. Thus we cannot neglect the mutual affinity of molecules and ions, their different tendencies of being adsorbed on an interface and so on. If this attraction between the lattice forming units is sufficiently low or lattice formation is not feasible due to some energy or other considerations, it is possible that no crystalline centre may be formed even though $c\phi$ values indicate a large probability of molecular impacts. In other words, it shows that under these circumstances the probability of *successful* molecular collision is very small inspite of large *unsuccessful* molecular encounters. The low mutual affinity among the molecules of the ammonium salts and among those of organic substances is shown by their easy subliming nature at low temperatures and their low melting points. According to Jaeger (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1917, 101, 1) the surface energy values σ , which may be in some way related to the mutual attraction of the lattice forming units of organic melts, are comparatively much low to those of the melts of ordinary inorganic electrolytes. This low affinity appears to be mainly responsible for the anomaly in most cases.

The ionic or molecular size or volume may explain some of the anomalies. Ions of larger volume will be required in a smaller number for the formation of stable crystal nucleus as compared to those of a smaller size. This means a higher probability of crystal nucleus formation in the former than in the latter. It appears, however, premature to apply this condition to individual cases.

The case of KClO_4 must be considered for the present an unexplained exception until some more light is thrown on the problem by further investigation. It may be suggested, however, that very low viscosity of its solutions may be to some extent responsible for this behaviour. But this explanation is obviously not enough.

The author is highly obliged to Dr. A. C. Chatterji for helpful criticism and valuable suggestions.